

Impact of Work-Life Balance on Job Satisfaction-A Case from Media Industry of Karachi

Author's Details:

⁽¹⁾Ali Sultan

Scholar, Greenwich University, Karachi, Pakistan. Email: mian6478@gmail.com

⁽²⁾Dr. Masood Hassan

Ph.D.,IoBM, Karachi, Pakistan and Visiting Faculty Greenwich, Karachi, Pakistan. Email: masoodhassan1@hotmail.com (**Corresponding Author**)

Abstract:

Employees of any organization or company are the most useful asset. Because employees run the organizations, they define organizations and companies. Not organizations and companies define them. Employees having job satisfaction highly contribute to the success of an organization or company. This research is done to discover the impact of work-life balance on job satisfaction. The data was collected from 130 participants by questionnaires. Then collected data were studied through SPSS (statistical packages for social sciences). A lot of research has been done on job satisfaction, but this is till lucrative for researchers to do research on this topic again and again. To create a satisfying employee society that will have positive impacts on the organizations and the country.

Keywords: Job Satisfaction, Work-Life Balance, Working Conditions, Work-Family Conflict

Introduction

As the global market is increasing day by day, the need for employees is increasing. To cater to the needs of the global. For the employee, it is important to have a work-life balance to have job satisfaction. Job satisfaction is a sense to have to complete a job without sacrificing personal life and enjoying the outcome of it. For that employee needs work-life balance. Work-life balance is the most essential thing to achieve for the employee. Work-life balance simply means finding the right equilibrium between the workforce and the individual private life. Developed countries have done already research on it. Developing countries have also started paying attention to the front to increase employee job satisfaction (Sobia, Farooq,& faryaal,2011). Employees are the most important treasure of the organization as they not only run the organization but also bring revenue to the organization.

In this century it is very difficult to achieve work-life balance because an employee can not simply leave their work at the workplace. These days employees are always connected to work through technology use such as emails and online meetings. which is not only disturbing by also affects the work-life balance drastically. According to the various work-life balance surveys, more than 60 % of the participants said that they are not able to find equilibrium between their private and professional lives. They must make tough choices even when their jobs and private life were not balanced (Subha,2013). A full-time average employee spends more than 35 hours a week in the office. And sometimes weekends have also been taken by the employer for the work. This not only makes employees tired but also ruins their work-life balance and mental health. The long working hour, work pressure, high demanding job, and use of sophisticated technology make it difficult for an employee to keep a balance between their job and work commitments (Nadeem & Abbas, 2009). An employee is always at work throughout their presence digitally and physically. This not only makes employe depress it also decreases the productivity of the employee. Maintaining employee work-life balance and helping him/her to achieve job satisfaction is an investment by the organization. Organizations should make policy which is enjoyed by the employee. If organizations want to retain their employees, then they should have an appropriate work-life balance policy (Agha, Azmi, & Irfan,2017). Employee satisfaction with organizational policy leads to greater organizational productivity as a result of employee performance (Sarwar, 2013). A balanced work-life score provides an organization with a productive and innovative employee (Greenhaus,2003).

Job satisfaction balance can be achieved through many aspects. Work-life balance is unable accomplished in a matter of days. It needs to be studied to get implied in the organizations. As the markets are growing widely

worldwide the demand for employees is also increasing with the increasing number of employees its organization and individual responsibility to take care of his/her work-life balance to have job satisfaction. Humans are psychologically driven species unless they don't have satisfaction in their life, they won't be happy and will continue to drown their selves in mental illness just for the sake of survival. Human physical and as well as mental health both are important to work properly. If one of them is not well-being, there is no sense to keep going. Because in the end, it will make no sense to drown yourself with the thought to swim above the ocean (Fereday & Oster,2010).

Problem Statement

Job satisfaction became an impressively major concern for employers and employees. Job satisfaction primarily deals with the employee having a sense of peace and calm when doing his/her work and it also deals with the productivity of the employee. As several studies have shown having job satisfaction brings positive change in the productivity of an employee. Organizations need to make an employee-friendly policy, which promotes work-life balance and job satisfaction ultimately. Organizations who are focused on employee job satisfaction are growing very fastly in the world. And the organizations which are just focused on their motive and revenue are now being placed in the end Ranking. Now the world is changing employee job satisfaction is as important as the company's revenue. Research has been done in the past on job satisfaction but with the respect to times, we need to update research to help employees and employers both to grow together and help the employee to have job satisfaction. Many organizational managers believe that salaries and financial benefits are the way to increase job satisfaction (Al-zoubi, 2012). Competition is increasing day by day among organizations. Employees know their goals, job satisfaction, and work-life balance. Organizations are spending huge amounts to come up with creative and practical ways to keep their employee satisfied with their jobs. Job satisfaction is the most important attitude in the field of organizational behaviors (Pandey, 2012).

Balance in work, and life, along with job satisfaction are becoming a need of every employee. As every employee wants to enjoy both their work and life. But it is not that easy to have job satisfaction. Whoever is having job satisfaction more than half of his life is sorted. As that person has zero concerns and regrets related to his work and will stay as long as he wants to and can be considered successful as well. That will have a very positive effect on his professional and personal life.

In our paper, we will investigate the impact of work-life balance on job satisfaction and other elements which affect job satisfaction.

Significance of Research

The significance of this quantitative research is very important as it shows the impact of the work-life balance on job satisfaction. Therefore, can also increase the productivity of the organization and its employees. This research may show some discoveries related to the employee how to achieve job satisfaction and what are the factors affecting the job satisfaction. Including how important it is to have a work-life balance to have job satisfaction. Several groups of organizations will also be interested in the results and conclusion of this research. These days every organization is trying to achieve a high level of productivity which is only possible after the job satisfaction of the employees. Furthermore, this research will be interesting for those individuals trying to find a work-life balance. In Pakistan, very few investigations are looked up on the impact of work-life balance on job satisfaction. Thus, they are not done recently. To fill the need to update research on the job satisfaction which is a very important factor for employees and society. According to the finance government Pakistan civilian labor report, in 2018 94 percent of society is the employee.

Job satisfaction needs to be studied in detail in the underdeveloping country. As the developed countries have done a lot of research on it and they are still doing it. To create a satisfying employee society that will have positive impacts on the organizations and the country. The definition of success has changed throughout time. In older times successful means how much capital you have now it is how satisfied are you with the work are you doing. To create a successful employee society, we need to study job satisfaction in detail in the underdeveloping country. It will be relatable if the person living in that country writes the research. So, I

believe my research will help to create job satisfied society and how to overcome the factors affecting it. The study of job satisfaction attempts to explain this behavior and this is important from a humanitarian and utilitarian perspective (Spector,1997).

Hypothesis

H1: Work-life balance significantly affects job satisfaction.

H2: Working conditions significantly affect job satisfaction.

H3: Work-family conflict significantly affects job satisfaction.

Research objectives

RO:1 To determine the impact of work-life balance on job satisfaction

RO:2 To analyze, the effect of working conditions on job satisfaction.

RO:3 To determine the relationship between the work-family conflict on job satisfaction.

Literature Review

The Concept of Work-Life Balance

Work-life balance simply means keeping work and life separately without losing you are sanity. There are three dimensions of work-life balance; 1) time balance which is allocating equal time to work and family, 2) involvement balance define as mental involvement in work and family issues, 3) and satisfaction balance which is equal satisfaction with family and work (Greenhaus et al., 2003).

Work and family are so correlated if there is an imbalance between one of them it will create an imbalance in another one automatically. For example, if you are disturbed by family issues, you'll be disturbed in your work no matter how hard you try to keep both separately. So, to overcome all these issues and maintain peace in life one must study work-life balance to achieve it in his/her personal life. Organizations are working very hard to give their employe a work-life balance through friendly environments, and physical and emotional support system initiatives. Because having a work-life balance, in the end, is a win-win for both employees and the organization.

Working Conditions

Working conditions are the terms and environment in which an employee works. They play an important part in job satisfaction. If the organization's policies are very strict and unlogical one will find it very difficult to work in that environment. Money and working condition are two major aspects an employee should see before signing up for that organization. For example, you don't want to miss any important event because of your work. Working conditions should be friendly and interactive. You can not get creative work done in 2 by 2 square compartments. Six dimensions of satisfaction with non-precautionary job aspects: environmental conditions, health security, efforts level, consideration by others, interest in the job, and job security has been analyzed (Ghineeti, 2007).

Working conditions is directly related to job satisfaction. Positive working conditions have a positive effect on job satisfaction and vice versa. working conditions are divided into two major parts terms and conditions and physical conditions. For big major organizations working conditions should be friendly, and precise, encouraging work consideration and promotions. Physical conditions should cooperate with human-friendly furniture. For example, most the offices have no proper seats and desk to work which cause back problem and other health issues in an employee. It should be well ventilated, so no one feels suffocated, etc. both the terms and conditions and physical conditions need to be good for job satisfaction. There are good and bad impacts of working conditions on the mental and physical health of the employee (Joyce, 2010).

Work-Family Conflict

Work and family both need human physical and emotional presence. Work-family conflict is a big factor in reducing job satisfaction. Everyone who has a family can relate to this. It is nothing less than a time bomb ticking on the head when you leave the office distressed, you'll be stressed at home and the fights and arguments will occur. They both are interlinked if one side is disturbed other will be too. Work-family conflict can also cause mental disorders, stress, depression, etc. in under developed countries having no such awareness of these issues it is believed that work-family conflicts are gender-based (May et al.,2004).

Job Satisfaction

Job satisfaction is explained as the constructive attitude of an employee toward how he/she is happy with their job. Job satisfaction has been a great topic for research for the last few decades. As humans are being aware of their physical plus emotional needs. Job satisfaction becomes a necessity of life. Because directly or indirectly it affects the other aspects of the human being's life. Job satisfaction is not only important on an individual level it is also important at organizational levels or multiorganizational levels. Job satisfaction is the most important attitude in the field of organizational behavior (Pandey,2012). For an employee's job, satisfaction is important for the happy well and the organization it is more productivity. Job satisfaction puts an unusually large impact on motivation, which in return affects productivity and the performance of the organizations (Aziri,2011).

Figure 1: Conceptual framework

Research Methodology

Data: The purpose of the study is to identify job satisfaction. Therefore, the existing readers of job satisfaction are the population of this study. The population size is Pakistan, and the sample size is the Karachi media industry. A questionnaire was used to collect data from media industry people of Karachi. Data was collected through floating questionnaires on WhatsApp and emails. 150 forms were circulated out of which 130 questionnaires were filled. So, the sample size consists of 120 people.

Respondent Profile: In research, the overall population 62% were men and 36 % were women and 2 percent prefer not to show their identity as male or female. 76% were single and 24% were married; 30% were at the age of 19-25, 40 percent were at the age of 41 percent, remaining 28 percent were older than 20 years. 19% of them were in the marketing industry, 10 percent were engineering industry, 18 percent were in the teaching industry, 7% were students, 5 percent were in the medical industry, and 5 percent were in the banking industry. The remaining 38 were housewives, and deputy commissioners and were in different industries.

Measurement of constructs: There were two parts to the survey questionnaire. Section one includes demographic questions including age, gender, profession, and marital status. While the other section contains the questions of the four constructs. Each construct has four questions. The items were evaluated on a 5-point Likert scale, with a highly disagree at 1 point and strongly agree at 5 points.

Statistical Techniques: For preliminary analysis and empirical testing of above mention hypothesis, the SPSS was utilized using the SPSS method. In estimating the complicated statistical relationship between latent variables.

Data Analysis & Discussion

Table 1

Age

Topic:	Ranks		
	Your age?	N	Mean Rank
Work_Life_Balance	less then 20	4	120.13
	20-29	92	60.20
	30-39	16	66.72
	above 40	16	73.13
	Total	128	

Table 2

Test Statistics^b

	Work-life balance
Kruskal-Wallis H	11.179
df	3
Asymp. Sig.	.011

a. Kruskal Wallis Test

b. Grouping Variable: Your age?

To evaluate the differences across four levels of ages for preferences to affect the work-life balance over job satisfaction was tested using the Kruskal Wallis test. The test revealed insignificant differences.

(Asymp, sig=0.011) in the preferncess to effect work life balance for four level of ages (age n<20), (age n= 20-29), (age n= 30-39) and (age n=above 40).

People in the age group 20-29 feel like they don't have a work-life balance, the age group of 30-39 feels the same way, and 40 and above feel the same way. But comparatively less than other age groups.

People of age group less than 20 feel like they have a work-life balance maybe because they have fewer responsibilities. People of the age group 20-29 feel like they are more affected maybe because they have less free time and more work burden.

Table 3

Gender

Topic:	Ranks		
	Your Gender?	N	Mean Rank
Work_Life_Balance	Male	84	68.90
	Female	44	56.10
	Total	128	

Table 4

Test Statistics^b

	Work-life balance
Kruskal-Wallis H	3.443
Df	1
Asymp. Sig.	.064

a. Kruskal Wallis Test

b. Grouping Variable: Your Gender?

To evaluate the differences across two levels of gender for preference to affect the work-life balance over job satisfaction was tested using the Kruskal Wallis test. The test revealed a significant difference. (Asymp, sig = 0.64). in the preferences to affect work-life balance for two levels of gender Male 84 responses, female 44 responses. Both feel they are satisfied with their work-life balance. There are no differences in work-life balance on the basics of genders.

Table 5
Profession

		Ranks	
Topic	Your profession?	N	Mean Rank
Work_Life_Balance	Student	17	49.53
	Teacher/Scholar	24	72.56
	Housewife	3	52.17
	Engineer	14	70.93
	Medical Sector	8	38.94
	Computing Sector	12	56.83
	Business/Banking Sector	12	70.29
	Advertising/Marketing Sector	25	76.14
	Others	13	60.19
	Total	128	

Table 6
Test Statistics

Work-life balance	
Kruskal-Wallis H	11.920
Df	8
Asymp. Sig.	.155

a. Kruskal Wallis Test
b. Grouping Variable: Your profession?

To evaluate the differences across 9 levels of professions for preferences to affect the work-life balance over job satisfaction was tested using the Kurusla Wallis test. The test revealed the insignificant. (Asymp sig=0.31) in the preferences to affect work-life balance for 9 levels of professions.

Professions dose not affect the work-life balance. But housewives comparatively do not feel balanced maybe they have housework to do. Singles feel like they have less work-life balance maybe they are university going and family pressure about getting married.

Table 7
Marital status

		Ranks	
Topic	Material status	N	Mean Rank
Work_Life_Balance	Single	97	60.51
	Married	31	76.98
	Total	128	

Table 8
Test Statistics^b

Work-life balance	
Kruskal-Wallis H	4.643
Df	1
Asymp. Sig.	.031

a. Kruskal Wallis Test
b. Grouping Variable: Material status

To evaluate the differences across 2 levels of marital status for preferences to affect the work-life balance over job satisfaction was tested using the Kruskal Wallis test. (Asymp, sig = 0.31) in the preference to affect work-life balance for 2 levels of marital status.

Married people are more satisfied with their work-life balance than single, maybe because they have family pressure, or education pressure they feel like they have over work to do. Until they don't have family offices assigned them over work to do and pay them less.

Conclusion

The main goal of the study was to investigate the effect of WLB, WC, and FC on job satisfaction. Research showed the relation between all independent variables and dependent variable. Thus companies and organizations should mandatory consider WLB, Wc, and FC to look after their employees' job satisfaction. WLB also showed a great positive effect on the productivity of the employee. The main difficulty to achieve JS was that employers were not able to give enough time to their families and their selves which directly affect their JB. The study also showed that JS is not based on gender, or profession but is based on marital status, age and the time individual have for their selves.

References

- Abbas, N. a. (2009). The Impact of Work-Life Conflict on Job Satisfaction of Employees in Pakistan. *International Journal of Business and Management*.
- Al-Zoubi, D. M. (2012). The shape of the relationship between salary and job satisfaction. *Far East Journal of Psychology and Business*.
- Aziri, b. (2011). Job satisfaction: a literature review. *Management research and practice*.
- Fereday, J., & Oster, C. (2010). Managing a work–life balance: the experiences of midwives working in a group practice setting. *Midwifery*, 26(3), 311-318.
- Ghinetti, P. (2007). The public-private job satisfaction differential in Italy. *Labour*.
- Greenhaus, J. H. (2003). The relation between work-family balance and quality of life. *Journal of Vocational Behavior*.
- Joyce, P. B. (2010). Flexible working conditions and their effects on employee health and wellbeing. *Cochrane Database of Systematic Reviews*.
- K. Agha, F. T. (2017). Work-Life Balance and Job Satisfaction: An Empirical study Focusing on Higher Education Teachers in Oman. *International Journal of Social Science and Humanity*.
- May, D. R., Gilson, R. L., & Harter, L. M. (2004). The psychological conditions of meaningfulness, safety and availability and the engagement of the human spirit at work. *Journal of occupational and organizational psychology*, 77(1), 11-37.
- Ms. Chetna Pandey, M. k. (2012). Impact of job satisfaction and organizational commitment on employee loyalty. *International journal of social science & interdisciplinary research*.
- Shagufta Sarwar, J. A. (2013). The Influence of Rewards and Job Satisfaction on Employees in the Service Industry. *The Business & Management Review*.
- Sobia Shujaat, F.-E.-A. C. (2011). Impact of Work-Life Balance on Employee Job Satisfaction in Private Banking Sector of Karachi. *Journal of Management and Social Sciences*.
- Spector, P. E. (1997). Job satisfaction: Application, assessment, causes, and consequences. *London: Sage*.
- Subha, M. T. (2013). A Study on Work-Life Balance Among WomenFaculties Working in Arts & Science Colleges with Special Reference to Coimbatore City. *Paripex -Indian Journal of Research*.